

USING ATOZMATH.COM SITE TO DETERMINE THE EIGENVALUES AND EIGENVECTORS OF A MATRIX

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Abstract: This article will consider using the atozmath.com site to determine the eigenvalue and eigenvectors of the matrix. Information will be provided that explains finding steps and calculate the eigenvalues of the given matrix. eigenvalues are the roots of the characteristic polynomial of the matrix, reflecting the algorithm for finding them and the appropriate formulas. The eigenvectors of the matrix belong to the corresponding vectors and provide information about the processes of determining them.

Key words: eigenvalues of a matrix, eigenvectors, Newton – Raphson method, characteristic polynomial, algorithm, iteration method to find out greatest eigenvalue.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada matritsaning xos son va xos vektorlarini aniqlash uchun atozmath.com saytidan foydalanish ko'rib chiqiladi. Matritsaning xos qiymatlarini topish qadamlari va ularni qanday hisoblashni tushuntiruvchi ma'lumotlar beriladi. Xos sonlar matritsaning xarakteristik ko'phadining ildizlari bo'lib, ularni topish algoritmi va mos formulalar aks ettiriladi. Matritsaning xos vektorlari mos xos vektorlarga tegishli bo'lib, ularni aniqlash jarayonlari haqida ma'lumot beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: matritsaning xos sonlari, xos vektorlari, Nyuton – Rafson usuli, xarakteristik ko'phad, algoritmi, eng katta xos sonni aniqlash uchun iteratsiya usuli.

Аннотация. В этой статье мы рассмотрим использование сайта atozmath.com для определения собственных значений и собственных векторов матрицы. Будет предоставлена информация, объясняющая шаги нахождения и вычисления собственных значений заданной матрицы. Собственные значения являются корнями характеристического полинома матрицы, отражая алгоритм их нахождения и соответствующие формулы. Собственные векторы матрицы принадлежат соответствующим векторам и дают информацию о процессах их определения.

Ключевые слова: собственные значения матрицы, собственные векторы, метод Ньютона – Рафсона, характеристический многочлен, алгоритм, итерационный метод нахождения наибольшего собственного значения.

x is any linearly independent vector, consisting x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n elements. $A - n \times n$ matrix (we see symmetric matrices for now. The reason is being that, most of the mathematical physics issues end with a symmetrical matrix). Ax – this is the operator performed on the x vector, linear transformation, it is reflected in another vector. If the vector being viewed as a result of the performed linear transformation is reflected in a parallel vector, we call it an eigenvector, i.e.

$Ax = \lambda x$ is parallel, in which x is eigenvector

So, $Ax = \lambda x$, λ – eigenvalue.

We can rewrite the resulting equation as follows:

$(A - \lambda I)x = 0$, standard form of eigenvalue problem.

$x = 0$ vector satisfies the equation, but we are looking for another solutions.

atozmath.com consists of several sections, such as Algebra, Matrix and Vector, Numerical methods, Statistical Methods, Geometry, Calculus, Pre-algebra. We see Matrix & Vector. In section matrix operators, fifth – eigenvalues and sixth – eigenvectors are calculators we need.

AtoZmath.com - Homework help (with all solution steps)	
Educational Level	Secondary school, High school and College
Program Purpose	Provide step by step solutions of your problems using online calculators (online solvers)
Problem Source	Your textbook, etc
Matrix & Vector Calculators (examples)	
1.1 Matrix operations 1. Addition/Subtraction of two matrix 2. Multiplication of two matrix 3. Division of two matrix 4. Power of a matrix 5. Transpose of a matrix 6. Determinant of a matrix 7. Adjoint of a matrix 8. Inverse of a matrix 9. Prove that any two matrix expression is equal or not 10. Minor of a matrix 11. Cofactor of a matrix 12. Trace of a matrix	
1.2 Matrix operations 1. Transforming matrix to Row Echelon Form 2. Transforming matrix to Reduced Row Echelon Form 3. Rank of matrix 4. Characteristic polynomial 5. Eigenvalues 6. Eigenvectors 7. Triangular Matrix 8. LU Decomposition using Gauss Elimination method 9. LU decomposition using Doolittle's method 10. LU decomposition using Crout's method 11. Diagonal Matrix 12. Cholesky Decomposition 13. QR Decomposition (Gram Schmidt Method) 14. QR Decomposition (Householder Method) 15. LQ Decomposition 16. Pivots of a Matrix 17. SVD - Singular Value Decomposition 18. Moore-Penrose Pseudoinverse of a Matrix 19. Power Method for dominant eigenvalue 20. Determinants using Sarrus Rule 21. Determinants using properties of determinants 22. Row Space 23. Column Space 24. Null Space	

The following window appears when we log in to the eigenvalues page. Here are some of the solutions to the example seen in the book “Numerical Methods” (A.Imamov, Namangan - 2021):

State of the calculator when the matrix is entered

We can click **Find** to see eigenvalues, **Cell** to change elements of the matrix or **Random** to select one of the sample examples provided by the applicaton.

Find Matrix Eigenvalues ...

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solution:

$$|A - \lambda I| = 0$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1-\lambda) & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & (3-\lambda) & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\therefore (1-\lambda) \times \begin{vmatrix} (3-\lambda) & 4 & 1 \\ 4 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} - 2 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 4 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} + 3 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & (3-\lambda) & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} - 4 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & (3-\lambda) & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & (1-\lambda) \\ 4 & 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\therefore (1-\lambda) \times (-36 + 6\lambda + 7\lambda^2 - \lambda^3) - 2 \times (-4 + 8\lambda + 2\lambda^2) + 3 \times (4 + 2\lambda - 3\lambda^2) - 4 \times (-44 - 8\lambda + 4\lambda^2) = 0$$

$$\therefore (-36 + 42\lambda + \lambda^2 - 8\lambda^3 + \lambda^4) + (8 - 16\lambda - 4\lambda^2) + (12 + 6\lambda - 9\lambda^2) + (176 + 32\lambda - 16\lambda^2) = 0$$

$$\therefore (\lambda^4 - 8\lambda^3 - 28\lambda^2 + 64\lambda + 160) = 0$$

$$\therefore (\lambda^4 - 8\lambda^3 - 28\lambda^2 + 64\lambda + 160) = 0$$

Roots can be found using newton raphson method

✦ Newton Raphson method for $x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160 = 0$

Characteristic polynomial of the matrix has been identified, and many of its roots can be found using Newton – Raphson method.

Note: Here $f(-2) = 0$, So Root of the equation = 0 is -2. But we will try to find out another root between 2 and 3

Here $x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160 = 0$

Let $f(x) = x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160$

$\therefore f'(x) = 4x^3 - 24x^2 - 56x + 64$

$x_0 = 3$

1st iteration :

$$f(x_0) = f(3) = 3^4 - 8 \times 3^3 - 28 \times 3^2 + 64 \times 3 + 160 = -35$$

$$f'(x_0) = f'(3) = 4 \times 3^3 - 24 \times 3^2 - 56 \times 3 + 64 = -212$$

$$x_1 = x_0 - \frac{f(x_0)}{f'(x_0)}$$

$$x_1 = 3 - \frac{-35}{-212}$$

$$x_1 = 2.83490566$$

2nd iteration :

$$f(x_1) = f(2.83490566) = 2.83490566^4 - 8 \times 2.83490566^3 - 28 \times 2.83490566^2 + 64 \times 2.83490566 + 160 = -1.27103892$$

$$f'(x_1) = f'(2.83490566) = 4 \times 2.83490566^3 - 24 \times 2.83490566^2 - 56 \times 2.83490566 + 64 = -196.5022464$$

$$x_2 = x_1 - \frac{f(x_1)}{f'(x_1)}$$

$$x_2 = 2.83490566 - \frac{-1.27103892}{-196.5022464}$$

$$x_2 = 2.82843734$$

3rd iteration :

$$f(x_2) = f(2.82843734) = 2.82843734^4 - 8 \times 2.82843734^3 - 28 \times 2.82843734^2 + 64 \times 2.82843734 + 160 = -0.00200156$$

$$f'(x_2) = f'(2.82843734) = 4 \times 2.82843734^3 - 24 \times 2.82843734^2 - 56 \times 2.82843734 + 64 = -195.88322952$$

$$x_3 = x_2 - \frac{f(x_2)}{f'(x_2)}$$

$$x_3 = 2.82843734 - \frac{-0.00200156}{-195.88322952}$$

$$x_3 = 2.82842712$$

Approximate root of the equation $x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160 = 0$ using Newton Raphson method is 2.82842712 (After 3 iterations)

n	x_0	$f(x_0)$	$f'(x_0)$	x_1	Update
1	3	-35	-212	2.83490566	$x_0 = x_1$
2	2.83490566	-1.27103892	-196.5022464	2.82843734	$x_0 = x_1$
3	2.82843734	-0.00200156	-195.88322952	2.82842712	$x_0 = x_1$

Now, using long division $\frac{x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160}{x - 2.82842712} = x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249$

+ Newton Raphson method for $x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249 = 0$

$\therefore x = 2$

Now, using long division $\frac{x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249}{x + 2} = x^2 - 7.17157287x - 28.28427126$

Now, $x^2 - 7.17157287x - 28.28427126 = 0$

$\therefore x = -2.82842713$ and $x = 10$

\therefore The eigenvalues of the matrix A are given by $\lambda = -2.82842713, -2, 2.82842712, 10$

When searching for a solution to the characteristic equation using the Newton-Rafson method, after three iterations, it was determined that its first eigenvalue was 2,82842712. The degree of characteristic polynomial is being reduced by deviding $(x - 2.82842712)$. When the Newton-Rafson method was again used for the resulting polynomial, it turned out that the letter eigenvalue was $x = 2$. When the multiplication was devided to $(x - 2)$ and the degree was lowered again, a square function was formed, and its roots were found to be $x_1 = -2.82842713$ and $x_2 = 10$.

Therefore, the eigenvalues of the given matrix were $\lambda = -2.82842713, -2, 2.82842712, 10$. In this case, the results were identical to the source from which the example was taken. Now we see corresponding eigenvectors:

Matrix operations

Method 6. Eigenvectors

Matrix Eigenvectors (Eigenspace) calculator

Matrix A :

1	2	3	4
2	3	4	1
3	4	1	2
4	1	2	3

Mode = Decimal

Decimal Place = 8

As we click the Find button, the eigenvalues and their corresponding vectors will begin to be shown step by step:

Find Matrix Eigenvectors (Eigenspace) ...

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solution:
 $|A - \lambda I| = 0$

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1-\lambda) & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & (3-\lambda) & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\therefore (1-\lambda) \times \begin{vmatrix} (3-\lambda) & 4 & 1 \\ 4 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} - 2 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & (1-\lambda) & 2 \\ 4 & 2 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} + 3 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & (3-\lambda) & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & (3-\lambda) \end{vmatrix} - 4 \times \begin{vmatrix} 2 & (3-\lambda) & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & (1-\lambda) \\ 4 & 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\therefore (1-\lambda) \times (-36 + 6\lambda + 7\lambda^2 - \lambda^3) - 2 \times (-4 + 8\lambda + 2\lambda^2) + 3 \times (4 + 2\lambda - 3\lambda^2) - 4 \times (-44 - 8\lambda + 4\lambda^2) = 0$$

$$\therefore (-36 + 42\lambda + \lambda^2 - 8\lambda^3 + \lambda^4) + (8 - 16\lambda - 4\lambda^2) + (12 + 6\lambda - 9\lambda^2) + (176 + 32\lambda - 16\lambda^2) = 0$$

$$\therefore (\lambda^4 - 8\lambda^3 - 28\lambda^2 + 64\lambda + 160) = 0$$

$$\therefore (\lambda^4 - 8\lambda^3 - 28\lambda^2 + 64\lambda + 160) = 0$$

Roots can be found using newton raphson method

+ Newton Raphson method for $x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160 = 0$

$$\therefore x = 2.82842712$$

Initially, the characteristic polynomial of the matrix were identified, and it was determined that the former eigenvalue for this was $x_1 = 2.82842712$. Step by step eigenvalues are found in the same way and the $\det(A - \lambda I)x = 0$ equation is solved to find each corresponding vector:

Now, using long division $\frac{x^4 - 8x^3 - 28x^2 + 64x + 160}{x - 2.82842712} = x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249$

+ Newton Raphson method for $x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249 = 0$

$$\therefore x = -2$$

Now, using long division $\frac{x^3 - 5.17157288x^2 - 42.627417x - 56.56854249}{x + 2} = x^2 - 7.17157287x - 28.28427126$

Now, $x^2 - 7.17157287x - 28.28427126 = 0$

$$\therefore x = -2.82842713 \text{ and } x = 10$$

\therefore The eigenvalues of the matrix A are given by $\lambda = -2.82842713, -2, 2.82842712, 10$

+ 1. Eigenvectors for $\lambda = -2.82842713$

$$v_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -2.41421356 \\ -1 \\ 2.41421356 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

2. Eigenvectors for $\lambda = -2$

$$A - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} + 2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 5 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now, reduce this matrix
interchanging rows $R_1 \leftrightarrow R_4$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 1 & 2 & 5 \\ 2 & 5 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_1 \leftarrow R_1 \div 4$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0.5 & 1.25 \\ 2 & 5 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_2 \leftarrow R_2 - 2 \times R_1$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0.5 & 1.25 \\ 0 & 4.5 & 3 & -1.5 \\ 3 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_3 \leftarrow R_3 - 3 \times R_1$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0.5 & 1.25 \\ 0 & 4.5 & 3 & -1.5 \\ 0 & 3.25 & 1.5 & -1.75 \\ 3 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_4 \leftarrow R_4 - 3 \times R_1$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0.5 & 1.25 \\ 0 & 4.5 & 3 & -1.5 \\ 0 & 3.25 & 1.5 & -1.75 \\ 0 & 1.25 & 1.5 & 0.25 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_2 \leftarrow R_2 \times 0.22222222$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0.5 & 1.25 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 3.25 & 1.5 & -1.75 \\ 0 & 1.25 & 1.5 & 0.25 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_1 \leftarrow R_1 - 0.25 \times R_2$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.33333333 & 1.33333333 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 3.25 & 1.5 & -1.75 \\ 0 & 1.25 & 1.5 & 0.25 \end{bmatrix}$$

$\lambda = -2$ is also considered a matrix $A - \lambda I$, made to look triangular multiplying to x vector to vanish, $(A - \lambda I)x = 0$.

$R_3 \leftarrow R_3 - 3.25 \times R_2$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.33333333 & 1.33333333 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.66666667 & -0.66666667 \\ 0 & 1.25 & 1.5 & 0.25 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_4 \leftarrow R_4 - 1.25 \times R_2$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.33333333 & 1.33333333 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.66666667 & -0.66666667 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.66666667 & 0.66666667 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_3 \leftarrow R_3 \times -1.5$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.33333333 & 1.33333333 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.66666667 & 0.66666667 \end{bmatrix}$$

$R_1 \leftarrow R_1 - 0.33333333 \times R_3$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.66666667 & -0.33333333 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.66666667 & 0.66666667 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_2 \leftarrow R_2 - 0.66666667 \times R_3$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.66666667 & 0.66666667 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_4 \leftarrow R_4 - 0.66666667 \times R_3$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The system associated with the eigenvalue $\lambda = -2$

$$(A + 2I) \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow x_1 + x_4 = 0, x_2 - x_4 = 0, x_3 + x_4 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow x_1 = -x_4, x_2 = x_4, x_3 = -x_4$$

\therefore eigenvectors corresponding to the eigenvalue $\lambda = -2$ is

$$v = \begin{bmatrix} -x_4 \\ x_4 \\ -x_4 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Let $x_4 = 1$

$$v_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

We can see the calculating process of the value by clicking on the + character at the beginning of the statement.

Corresponding eigenvector for $\lambda_3 = 2.82842712$ is

$$v_3 = (0.41421356, -1, -0.41421356, 1)$$

eigenvector for $\lambda_4 = 10$

$$v_4 = (1, 1, 1, 1).$$

Using paragraph 19, we can determine the extreme eigenvalue of matrix using Power method.

+ 3. Eigenvectors for $\lambda = 2.82842712$

$$v_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.41421356 \\ -1 \\ -0.41421356 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

+ 4. Eigenvectors for $\lambda = 10$

$$v_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

- 13. QR Decomposition (Gram Schmidt method)
- 14. QR Decomposition (Householder Method)
- 15. LQ Decomposition
- 16. Pivots of a Matrix
- 17. SVD - Singular Value Decomposition
- 18. Moore-Penrose Pseudoinverse of a Matrix
- 19. Power Method for dominant eigenvalue
- 20. Determinants using Sarrus Rule
- 21. Determinants using properties of determinants
- 22. Row Space
- 23. Column Space
- 24. Null Space

I have entered the previous matrix to check whether it is right or wrong.

Matrix operations

Method

Power Method for finding dominant eigenvalue calculator

Matrix A :

1	2	3	4
2	3	4	1
3	4	1	2
4	1	2	3

$x_0 = [1, 0, 0, 0, 0]$

Mode =

Decimal Place =

I chose the vector $x_0 = (1, 0, 0, 0)$ as an initial vector. Each time the Ax action is performed, the vector is divided its greatest element, and new x vector is found:

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_1 = \frac{1}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.75 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

2nd Iteration

$$Ax_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.75 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.5 \\ 6 \\ 5.5 \\ 6 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_2 = \frac{1}{7.5} \begin{bmatrix} 7.5 \\ 6 \\ 5.5 \\ 6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.8 \\ 0.73333333 \\ 0.8 \end{bmatrix}$$

3rd Iteration

$$Ax_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.8 \\ 0.73333333 \\ 0.8 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 8 \\ 8.13333333 \\ 8.53333333 \\ 8.66666667 \end{bmatrix}$$

Find Power Method for finding dominant eigenvalue ...

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solution:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

1st Iteration

$$Ax_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_3 = \frac{1}{8.66666667} \begin{bmatrix} 8 \\ 8.13333333 \\ 8.53333333 \\ 8.66666667 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.92307692 \\ 0.93846154 \\ 0.98461538 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

4th Iteration

$$Ax_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.92307692 \\ 0.93846154 \\ 0.98461538 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.75384615 \\ 9.6 \\ 9.50769231 \\ 9.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_4 = \frac{1}{9.75384615} \begin{bmatrix} 9.75384615 \\ 9.6 \\ 9.50769231 \\ 9.6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.98422713 \\ 0.97476341 \\ 0.98422713 \end{bmatrix}$$

5th Iteration

$$Ax_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.98422713 \\ 0.97476341 \\ 0.98422713 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.829653 \\ 9.83596215 \\ 9.88012618 \\ 9.88643533 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_5 = \frac{1}{9.88643533} \begin{bmatrix} 9.829653 \\ 9.83596215 \\ 9.88012618 \\ 9.88643533 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.99425654 \\ 0.9948947 \\ 0.99936184 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

6th Iteration

$$Ax_5 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.99425654 \\ 0.9948947 \\ 0.99936184 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.98213146 \\ 9.97064454 \\ 9.96171027 \\ 9.97064454 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_6 = \frac{1}{9.98213146} \begin{bmatrix} 9.98213146 \\ 9.97064454 \\ 9.96171027 \\ 9.97064454 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.99884925 \\ 0.99795423 \\ 0.99884925 \end{bmatrix}$$

7th Iteration

$$Ax_6 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.99884925 \\ 0.99795423 \\ 0.99884925 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.98695819 \\ 9.98721391 \\ 9.99104974 \\ 9.99130546 \end{bmatrix}$$

After iteration, we can see that we have come very close to the result. It turned out

10th Iteration

$$Ax_9 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.99996621 \\ 0.99996723 \\ 0.99999898 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.9998976 \\ 9.99983002 \\ 9.99976653 \\ 9.99983002 \end{bmatrix}$$

and by scaling we obtain the approximation

$$x_{10} = \frac{1}{9.9998976} \begin{bmatrix} 9.9998976 \\ 9.99983002 \\ 9.99976653 \\ 9.99983002 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.99999324 \\ 0.99998689 \\ 0.99999324 \end{bmatrix}$$

that the largest eigenvalue is $\lambda = 9.9998976 \cong 10$ and the largest eigenvector $x = (1, 1, 1, 1)$ corresponding to it.

\therefore The dominant eigenvalue $\lambda = 9.9998976 \cong 10$

and the dominant eigenvector is :

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0.99999324 \\ 0.99998689 \\ 0.99999324 \end{bmatrix} \cong \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

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